

Figure Z15

Figure Z15: Cross-tissue communication at the cell type level. (A and C) Cross-tissue ligand-receptor networks between a pair of tissues and in diet (A) or training (C) comparisons. Cell types (nodes) are shaped by tissue (diamond: scWAT, circle: vWAT, square: skeletal muscle), coloured by cell type, and sized by outdegree. Ligand-receptor interactions (edges) are directed, from ligand to receptor, and coloured by effect direction (pink up-regulated, blue: down-regulated). **(B and D)** The number of differentially interactive ligand-receptor pairs that are up- and down-regulated between a pair of tissues and in diet (B) or training (D) comparisons. A list of abbreviations used in this figure appear in the Methods.